

An Analysis of Language Borrowing among Algerian University Students Using Online Facebook Conversations

Messaouda Annab

Abstract—The rapid development of technology has led to an important context in which different languages and structures are used in the same conversations. This paper investigates the practice of language borrowing within social media platform, namely, Facebook among Algerian Vernacular Arabic (AVA) students. In other words, this study will explore how Algerian students have incorporated lexical English borrowing in their online conversations. This paper will examine the relationships between language, culture and identity among a multilingual group. The main objective is to determine the cultural and linguistic functions that borrowing fulfills in social media and to explain the possible factors underlying English borrowing. The nature of the study entails the use of an online research method that includes ten online Facebook conversations in the form of private messages collected from Bachelor and Masters Algerian students recruited from the English department at the University of Oum El-Bouaghi. The analysis of data revealed that social media platform provided the users with opportunities to shift from one language to another. This practice was noticed in students' online conversations. English borrowing was the most relevant language performance in accordance with Arabic which is the mother tongue of the chosen sample. The analysis has assumed that participants are skilled in more than one language.

Keywords—Borrowing, language performance, linguistic background, social media.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS paper examines practical examples of borrowing that have been identified within students' online conversations.

Algeria is a country where for historical reasons different languages can be identified, notably Arabic (Standard and Vernacular), Berber, French and more recently English. Many Algerian students make use of all of these languages in their daily lives. The AVA is the mother tongue of the majority of the population; while Berber is also the native language of a minority of Algerians. In schools, Standard Arabic is the first language; French is considered as a second language and English is a foreign language. Accordingly, Algerian students tend to switch, mix and borrow words/phrases from other languages; there is a long-established practice to use French, and recently English is becoming more frequently used whilst it was not used a few years ago. The recent practice of borrowing from English has integrated Algerians daily language uses in different contexts.

M. Annab is with the University of Northampton, Faculty of Education and Humanities, Waterside Campus, University Drive, Northampton, NN1 5PH (e-mail: messaouda.annab@northampton.ac.uk).

This research aims to explain the impact of social media on language borrowing in the Algerian context. This study was conducted to identify lexical borrowing in online Facebook conversations of AVA students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are limited studies available on conducting social media research, since social media analysis is a newly emerging field of research [1]. Social media research is becoming more popular due to the vast wealth of data that are easily accessible to researchers through the internet [2]. Due to this lack of study on social media, this research identifies whether the use of social media chat rooms may show that AVA students borrow from English in their conversations. In this study, borrowing can be defined as a word, a phrase or even a sentence which have been taken from one language and used in another language. Similarly, Haugen [3] defines borrowing as being “a word, a phrase or an idea that somebody has taken from another person's work or from another language and is used in his own”. These borrowed words or also called ‘loan words’ can be identified in monolinguals' speech due to the intensity of contact between languages that facilitates the inclusion of foreign words.

A. Types of Borrowing

Treffers-Daller [4] traces the history of studies of linguistic borrowing. She identifies two subcategories of borrowing: ‘lexical borrowing’ and ‘grammatical borrowing’. This research makes use of these same categories.

1. Lexical Borrowing

Most researchers agree that “lexical borrowing” is widespread in the languages of the world [4]. Nelson-Sathi [5], for instance, defines lexical borrowing as the “transfer of a word from a donor language to a recipient language”. In this subcategory, other divisions can be identified: loanwords, loan blends, loan translations, and loan shifts.

According to Haugen, “The term loanword had already been established to designate vocabulary whose basic form and meaning are taken directly from another language, then integrated with lesser or greater fidelity into the phonological and grammatical systems of the matrix language” cited in [6]. Therefore, loanwords are considered to be lexical items that have been transferred from one language to another and have been integrated into the borrowing language but have retained their basic form and meaning with more or less differences at

the level of phonology or grammar from the donor language.

Haugen cited in [7] defines a “loan blend” as “a combination of native and borrowed morphological material”. In this regard, one part of native language is kept as it is and the other part is substituted for another element that belongs to the borrower language. Pyles and Algeo cited in [8] introduces an example of such a hybrid word form in “mechanics” where the native ending -ics was affixed to a Latin word “mechanicus”.

For Haugen [9], “loan translation” is “morpheme-by-morpheme translation”. For example, the English word “Superman” is a loan translation for the German word “Übermensch” and this process of borrowing is also called calque [10]. “Moment of truth” is another loan translation example given by Yule [8] which is originally derived from Spanish: “el momento de la verdad”.

“Loan shifts” represent the semantic transfer that consists of a shifted meaning of a native pattern to cover an introduced concept [3]. In other words, the form is native; while the meaning is imported. As an example, the verb “controleren” originally from the Dutch meaning “to check”; however, at a later stage it acquired the English meaning of “control” which means “to have power over” [4].

2. Grammatical Borrowing

Appel and Muysken [11] defined “grammatical borrowing” as “the incorporation of foreign rules into a language”. This involves changes in the syntax and the morphology of the patterns of the borrower language such as: word formation and inflection. For Appel and Muysken [11], grammatical borrowing occurs in five different ways.

Firstly, “convergence” is “the achievement of structural similarity in a given aspect of the grammar of two or more languages, assumed to be different at the onset of contact” [11]. This shows that similarities increase according to the coexistence of two languages for a long time. Generally, convergence starts at the phonetic level, then moves to affect the syntactic and grammar of both languages.

Secondly, due to the fact that wherever two languages are in constant contact involves inevitably the “cultural influence” of the dominant language on the other language; cultural influence is an important factor that has an impact on grammatical borrowing. Lexical borrowing is the result of this influence which tends to fill the lexical gap in the recipient language [6].

“Relexification” as the third type was first introduced by Muysken [12] on the basis of his study about patterns of a mixed language spoken in Ecuador, that results from a vernacular variety quechua with Spanish vocabulary collected from media language. After data analysis, Muysken found out that the mixture of languages have resulted in some changes. He, therefore, defined relexification as “a mental process that builds new lexical entries by copying the lexical entries of an already established lexicon and replacing their phonological representations derived from another language” [12].

Possible changes may occur in a language. The speakers of a certain language may acquire a different language and

consider it as a second language if they are brought into a region different from their own due to the cultural and political prestige. Muysken [12] refers to this as “substitution influence” and this was considered as the fourth type of grammatical borrowing.

The fifth type involves the use of highly complicated expressions of a “prestigious language” that are a result of imitation through different European languages and only grammar aspects can be recognised.

B. Reasons for Borrowing

Explaining why languages borrow words is generally difficult as there is no accurate answer. In the case of the Algerians, there are several possible factors which lead to lexical borrowing. For instance:

1. Lexical gap

Borrowing may occur to fill the lexical gaps in the recipient language [13]. In this situation, borrowing is caused by a ‘lexical need’ for AVA students who are the focal point of the research gap. In particular, borrowing is used to satisfy scientific and technological domains [14]. Similarly, Campbell cited in [15] claims that it is common for speakers of a language to borrow words from another language, primarily because of need.

2. Internet Usage

Increased use of English on the internet is possibly influencing other languages. English is increasingly the language of global communication through its economic, technological and cultural power. It is estimated that no language can make a progress or succeed as an international medium of communication without a strong power [16]. Access to online information amongst geographically scattered people [17] may cause people to realize that their perspectives, behaviours, and language styles are different from each other according to the geographic association in the world. Thus, using English on the internet is a reason that can lead AVA students to borrow lexis. This can be linguistically confirmed by analyses of instances of borrowing which are predominantly linked to different semantic fields, for example technological advancement, international relations and the media [18].

3. Social Media

Social online activities increased through the emergence of social network sites by the end of the first decade of the 2000s. Online interaction such as text messages, e-mails, instant messages and chat have not only changed the way in which people interact but also have impacted the language use [17].

4. World Language

English is a world language [16]. English serves as an international lingua franca in many fields, hence it has become more prevalent in international media such as radio, TV and especially the internet which is the most global of them all [19]. This results in ‘loan words’ [20] which are integrated in the grammatical system of the second language and become

part of its lexicon.

5. Speech Community

Another factor in borrowing is that people use different languages according to the social factors in the speech community [21]. Fishman [22] describes language use in five domains: family, friendship, religion, education and employment. He analyses the factors in typical interactions in any domain: addressee, setting, topic and variety. It is believed that AVA students tend to switch between language varieties according to the situations in which they find themselves to discuss a particular topic.

6. Cultural Values

AVA users are multilingual and hence have access to different cultures as each language is more closely identified with certain cultural values [23]. Therefore, lexical borrowing is used to signal switches between the different cultural values connected to their linguistic repertoire.

7. Multiple Identities

A more recent theory concerns multiple identities. According to this, it is possible that AVA students borrow from English to perform new identities [24]. In this sense, borrowing from English may serve more than communicative functions, but also to identify speakers. Spolsky [25] states that hearing someone speaks can immediately let humans guess about the person's gender, educational level, profession and age. He also argues that beyond this individual matter, a language is a powerful symbol of national and ethnic identity. For example, Ibrahim [26] researched identity construction among African students in Canada. He pointed out that these students forged their identities of becoming "black" with all the cultural associations in North America through their adopting of black American linguistic style.

C. Related Theories

1. Halliday Model

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) is an approach to language that is used for a number of purposes, for example, language education and discourse analysis. Halliday's model studies language through its function rather than its structure. His traditional model is more interested in the manner by which language is utilised in social settings so as to obtain a specific target [27]. In other words, SFL is less interested in how language is represented, than in focusing on the discourse produced in the form of written or oral language and what the produced texts contain. Foremost, SFL has been used to shed light on the use of language for the purposes of meaning construction in the sense that users cannot fulfil the purposes of communications if utterances are not addressed to a particular contextual or cultural matter [28]. This means that SFL pays attention to meanings of language in use in the textual processes in social life. The context is one of the central concerns to analyse a text in SFL because it is integrated to the process of making meaning. Moreover, it is not possible to grasp the meaning of what the user utters or writes unless there is kind of familiarity with the context

embedded [29]. Fundamentally, language is related to a number of contexts, these contexts are: the context of culture (Genres) and the context of situation (Register). To Halliday cited in [27], the context of situation has three strands in which the aspects of the context are linked to the language used so as to create text. These strands are as the following:

- **Field:** indicates the topic discussed or talked about. In this research, three topics were extracted from the online data analysis; education, religion and sports.
- **Tenor:** is about who is involved in the communication trend and what the relationship between participants is. AVA students from the department of English were the targeted participants in this research project.
- **Mode:** indicates the form of language playing in the interaction (spoken or written). In this project, written form was used by the participants.

The three Register variables discussed above were used to explain people's perceptive understanding in which individuals use different kinds, different resources and different parts from the language system [27].

2. Fishman Model

The framework of this paper is also based on Fishman's [30] model of 'domains of language use'. These domains refer to contextualized spheres of communication, for example: home, friendship, work, education, religion. Fishman cited in [31] states that these domains may differ in number and designation from one bilingual or multilingual setting to another depending on the "socio-cultural dynamics" of the particular setting. Topic is an important factor in such domains. That is to say, if a group in a multilingual situation tends to handle a specific topic in a specific language, this may be because this topic belongs to a domain in which that language is dominant in this group. Thus, they use what is appropriate to the domain, topic and the expected pattern of behaviour [32]. This model is relevant to this research since AVA students are multilinguals. It is assumed that language maintenance may differ from one domain to another. Some domains seem to resist language maintenance more than others. This model of analysis has been thought to be applicable and a feasible model to describe the general patterns of distribution of languages in communities. As Fishman cited in [32] notes, this domain is used in "those speech communities that are characterized by widespread and relatively stable multilingualism."

III. METHODOLOGY

Ten AVA students between 20 to 30 years old from the English department of the University of Oum El Bouaghi were the subjects of this research. The reason for choosing that number is to have manageable results because findings from large groups take too long to process. The participants were from two levels: Bachelors and Masters. The subjects are university students because they have an educational level that enables them to be aware of their use of languages. This is a non-random technique.

Social media sites, discussion forums, and chat rooms are

considered as fertile sources of data and can be subjected to analysis [33]. Henn [34] considers that using Facebook for qualitative studies is a suitable method for conducting research with younger groups. Facebook is considered as providing a great stock of feedback in a relatively short period of time for qualitative subject analysis. All participants in this research have already had Facebook accounts in order to be included. The participants had the freedom to choose which Facebook conversations could be used in the analysis. As a result, no personal or sensitive information was disclosed. The interaction on Facebook tends to be in the form of private messages between two people. Both participants in any conversation agreed to send the researcher their discourse on the site. 50 pages of open conversations were collected covering a range of different topics through a Facebook private chat room source. The nature of this research study is qualitative. Thematic analysis was the method used as part of the discourse analysis of the research data.

IV. DATA DESCRIPTION AND ANALYSIS

Having read participants' data, three topics or themes were extracted; education, sports and religion. Kanchev et al. [35], claim that online discussions have a naturally emerging structure that can be beneficial in extracting the required information. These themes helped in identifying the cultural and linguistic factors that causes language use depending on the topic discussed. The participants' data are analysed in terms of borrowing patterns, the contextual variables and the different contexts in which the borrowing occurred during social media interactions. Examples of Facebook private message conversations from different participants are presented and classified in themes as the following: education, sports and religion.

Table I presents the brackets used to highlight which language was used in students' examples.

Brackets	Name	Use
()	parenthesis	English
{ }	curly	French
[]	square	AVA
< >	angle	Standard Arabic (SA)

A. Education

Participant: (well hhh) (I'm late if this word describes the situation) {apart sa} [welah hmd]. (1)

Translation: well (laughing) I am late if this word describes the situation apart from that I swear I am fine thank God.

The other person: [hhh hmd].

Translation: laughing, thank God.

Participant: [hehe hada win fhamt]....(cool)!! [ana li mdawakhni] (authors name first time mention) " [lazem] (full name) ". (2)

Translation: oh right, I understand now, the thing that is confusing me is the authors' name first time mention "it has to be full name".

The other person: (now I'll go take a nap).

Participant: [rani applikit fiha] (and they asked for my skype for the interview). (3)

Translation: I applied in it and they asked for a skype interview.

The other person: (sorry) [raho trisity ra7 hada win ja asm7ili].

Translation: Sorry for the power blackout, electricity is now restored, please forgive me.

Following Halliday's model of SFL, the field of these conversations covers an educational topic that was discussed by different participants. The tenor as described by Halliday cited in [27] is the subject under study. In this case the tenor refers to the AVA students of English, and the mode for Halliday is written form. As it is shown in the presented examples, the chosen participants have the ability to speak three languages; Arabic, French and English. However, the use of Arabic and English can be widely seen in students' conversations. Example (1) shows that the participant started the conversation with English then inserted French and finally shifted to Arabic. This participant wanted to show his extreme worry about writing his dissertation through expressing it in three languages. The use of the French phrase "apart sa" in this example is considered as a cultural influence of the grammatical borrowing type. This could imply that no equivalent words are used for this purpose in AVA or SA. Therefore, the use of "apart sa" could be classified as filling in the lexical gap in the recipient language. The participant in example (2) shows excitement expressing his understanding through the use of the English word "cool". This could also be considered as a western cultural influence that is not matched into a similar word in AVA or SA and it could be taken from social networks. This is another example of filling in the lexical gap in the recipient language. Example (3), however, presents an Arabic/English pattern, it is clearly seen that "applikit" in this example presents an Arabic inflection. The use of the Arabic bound morpheme "ikit" was marked with the English root "apply" which means "I applied" as one singular person. In this context, the participant seemed to apply the Arabic grammatical rule on an English borrowed word.

B. Sports

Participant: {ahh wé} (capital one cup). [yaw mawalitch ntab3] (foot) [m3a] {memoir} [hedi rabi ysabarna w khlas rani] (npushi) [f rohi frete]. (4)

Translation: oh really capital one cup, I am not into football anymore because of this dissertation may God let us patient that's it.

The other person: (I wish "Arsenal" good luck for tonight's match).

Participant: {les joueurs} [te3 doka makene makene]. {Ballon} [wela ma3endou hata me3na]. (5)

Translation: players nowadays are not that good. Recently, football is not that interesting to me.

The other person: [rani] {d'accord} [m3ak].

Translation: I agree with you.

This small conversation introduces sports as the discussion field in this section. AVA students of English present the tenor, whereas; the mode is a written form discussion. Both of the participants and the other person seem to have the same bilingual identity in which they master French and English besides Arabic. In (4), the participant functioned three different languages that have various syntactical systems. This participant seems to shift from one language to another throughout the same segment. However, his use of language seems to have abbreviations as in “wé” that means “yes” in English and the lexical borrowing “npushi” that shows no respect at none of the phonological, morphological and syntactical level. This item is a “loan blend” type of borrowing that consists of two Arabic bound morphemes “n” and “i” associated with an English root “push”. This lexical item has a singular meaning which is “I push”. Moving to example (5), the participant seems to be disappointed when giving his opinion about football. Unlike (4), the participant in this example presented two different languages; he first started in French, then switched to Arabic, back to French and ended the sentence in Arabic. The use of the French terms “les joueurs” and “ballon” seem to have no equivalent in AVA. Hence, they could be classified as a cultural influence to fill the lexical gap in the recipient language which is Arabic. Moreover, these words/phrases are generally used by many Algerians in the context of sports.

C. Religion

Participant: (Just) ["twakli 3la Rabi"] (and everything will be OK), [inchallah]. (6)

Translation: just have faith in God and everything will be OK, if God wants.

The other person: (I hope so) [Inchallah], < ti9a fi Allah > [hiya kolshi].

Translation: I hope so...if God wants, trust in God is everything.

Participant: {oui}.... <Ti9a wel imane bi Allah> [ywaslouk l mobtagak]. (7)

Translation: Yes...trust and faith in God leads to what you want.

Participant: (Have a good day), <wa 3alaikom salam wa ra7mato Allah>. (8)

Translation: have a good day, peace be upon you and the mercy of God.

These examples were taken from two different students' online conversations that show a religious concern. According to Halliday cited in [27], the field is religion, AVA students of English represent the tenor and the mode is a spoken form. The main discussion was about having faith in God; the participant in (6) and (7) is trying to give advice to the other person who seems to have a problem. Example (6) highlights an English/ Arabic borrowing pattern; this participant started in English, then shifted to AVA back to English and last shift to Arabic. The use of AVA in this sentence is marked by religious phrases and words as highlighted in angel brackets. For instance, “inchallah” is a word that Muslims always tend

to use when they are talking about something they are hoping it happens; this Arabic term is presented using Latin characters. The type of the discussed example can be classified as English loanwords associated with Arabic use. The participant in example (7) showed a different linguistic pattern which is French/SA/AVA. The word “oui” is widely used by many Algerians, the use of SA and AVA, however; indicates that the participant shifted to talk about a religious matter in which she is advising the other person to keep faith in God so as to achieve their goals. As shown in example (8), a different participant in (8) seems to vary his language use. He, first, initiated his speech with English and shifted to SA so as to express his Muslim identity. The use of “wa 3alaikom salam wa ra7mato Allah” is a salutation in Islam used by Muslims and means peace be upon you. In this respect, the use of the capital letter “A” in the name of God which is “Allah” was noticed in both examples (7) and (8) to show the holy spirit of Muslims.

V. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This paper aimed at highlighting the impact of social media and, particularly, Facebook chat room on students' language use. Online users of this research have shown a great interest in the Facebook chat platform because it enables interacting with different languages. The recorded conversations include three languages (Arabic, French and English) depending on the context. Several examples of how borrowing contributes to language shift within other languages were presented within Facebook conversations such as: a shift from Arabic to English and then to French among AVA students' online speech. This can be illustrated in the example below: (*well hhh (I'm late if this world describes the situation) {apart sa} [welah hmd]*).

Translation: well (laughing) I am late if this world describes the situation apart from that I swear I am fine thank God.

Note: the key indicators for each language are presented in Table I.

In this context, the online platform Facebook provided the users with opportunities to shift from one language to another. This was witnessed in students' online written forms (as shown in the above example). Online chatrooms as a communication technology provide speakers with opportunities for a face-to-face interaction through a written form [36]. The data show that participants tend to show their linguistic background in mastering more than one language in which they find it easy to borrow within an online circle. The findings of this research highlighted that borrowing from English into Arabic and Arabic into English patterns recorded the highest language shift in students' conversations. Belmihoub [37] in his article “English in a multilingual Algeria” claims that “the internet today is a bottom-up platform for Algerian English users to reach the higher ends of the cline. The advent of such social media spaces as Facebook and YouTube offers a platform for Algerian youth to express themselves in English and become users of this language in an unprecedented fashion”. Therefore, it could possibly be said

that social media may help the users to borrow from other languages through providing a convenient communication that assists to write Arabic in Latin scripts (this has been marked in the online dataset presented in examples 1 to 8) using various acronyms than to transform the keyboard to Arabic characters. This medium of communication helped the user to acquire, for instance, new words and acronyms. Within Facebook platform, 'hmd' and 'wé' were repeatedly marked in students' conversations instead of full words. Hmd is an acronym derived from Arabic, but then Romanised using the keyboard. Wé is a French word written in English phonetics. These examples are commonly used by the chosen sample in an online written form. In this context, Matras [36] claims that text messaging and chatrooms encourage the occurrence of non-standard forms of written language that contains linguistic improvisation and creativity. Matras concluded that multilingual speakers create a complex repertoire of linguistic expressive structures when interacting with other individuals. This is due to the provided networking opportunities that enable speakers to use such a multilingual repertoire.

Regarding language form and structure, Arabic was introduced in different forms. First, Arabic speech in Latin scripts were highlighted in 'red', in examples (1) to (8). Second, new words were introduced through the use of English root with Arabic suffix and prefixes, for example, "applikit" (I applied) in example (3) and "npushi" (I push) in example (4).

A. Education

The findings in the first theme show that education tends to be the topic where borrowing from English language is most likely used. Shamimah's study cited in [13] shows that English borrowings were used in educational, scientific, technological, economic and political. According to the subjects of her study, the reason for the preference was because English loan words sounded more elegant, modern and sophisticated.

Another finding is the use of individual words/phrases in English and French within Arabic clauses does not relate to the speakers' gender, but to their educational level. Presumably, AVA students' use of French when discussing education topic was limited in their online interactions to some lexical items which they inserted in Arabic utterances. The research sample is students with a good command of English and French. Their conversations show many examples of borrowing and code-switching which are more frequent in some contexts such as education.

The findings also show that having different educational backgrounds lead AVA students to borrow from English in order to express identity. Furthermore, as previously mentioned, the results show that all the speakers use different languages in particular situation (context) and for particular purposes. This suggests why this code of borrowing has been perhaps developed among the chosen sample. In other words, this may explain why they use more English and Arabic constituents.

B. Sports

Having highlighted English/Arabic, Arabic/English patterns as the most dominant patterns in relation to education, Arabic/French, Arabic/English/French linguistic patterns were highlighted by the participants when discussing sports topic. This may indicate that the content or the nature of the topic required the use of these patterns. Arabic, however, displayed the fluent language that the speakers used throughout their writings and speech. Furthermore, in many cases, the findings of this research suggested that there is no one-to-one equivalent in AVA which required students to switch/borrow from other languages. SA, however, seemed to be ignored by the chosen sample.

C. Religion

Unlike the other themes, religion represents a different implication of languages, most participants generated AVA/SA pattern. For this topic, it was marked that some participants preferred to insert Standard Arabic in their writings and used less borrowing from both English and French when talking about their own experiences that are related to their beliefs and trust in God. In other words, these participants wanted to show their attachment to their religion and its blessed language. Overall, it could be said that each topic represents a certain degree of language use preferred by participants. In some cases, like this, it could be said that participants make appropriate decisions about the use of one language rather than the other according to the topic they are discussing.

D. Further Discussion Analysis

The findings revealed that there are other factors than the topic discussed and the setting which was Facebook. These identified factors helped in the occurrence of language mixing and borrowing in particular.

The use of various language codes in a conversation is also influenced by the addressee. In other words, the speaker produces speech considering the addressee's language understanding so as to convey the message. Within prior literature, Halliday cited in [27] called this factor as "tenor" in his classification of the context of situation. The addressee as presented in this research is considered as an important factor in language mixing. Additionally, Dweik and Qawar [38] claim that the target audience is one of the factors that determine the speaker's language choice. Findings revealed that the speakers tend to borrow/switch depending on the addressee's language proficiency. This claim can be supported in the participant examples (1) to (8) in which the participants respected the other person's language proficiency. In other words, they both understand the three languages used (Arabic, French, and English).

Analysing the language used in this study presented identity as one of the factors that participants displayed in this study. Therefore, it could be possibly said that borrowing from English into Arabic may serve more than communicative functions but also to identify speakers. In this case, it is used to demonstrate that AVA are students of English. This identity

has been manifested in the speakers' writings conversations. Another assumption that could be possibly generated is that speakers attempted to use more than one language in order to show their bilingual/multilingual identity.

Spolsky [25] states that hearing someone speak can immediately let people guess about the person's gender, educational level, profession and age. Level of education contributed to this research study as a new factor to indicate the use of more than one language in one segment. This indicates that there might be a need to practise English as a student of English which leads to the assumption that many students may borrow from other languages so as to express their educational background. In other words, the insertion of large English borrowing within Arabic is a fact that has been observed with speakers of a high level of education (see Section IV A, B, and C examples).

VI. CONCLUSION

This research contributed to the evolution of language borrowing on social media and its impact on students' language development. Precisely, findings revealed several patterns of borrowing depending on a certain topic (education, sports, and religion). English and AVA were predominantly displayed within the online conversations of the chosen sample. An important contribution to this study was the level of education of the research participants that resulted in large English borrowings.

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